

Prevalence of Hypertension among Asymptomatic Patients During Screening in the Primary Health Care Center, Riyadh, Saudi Arabia

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Abstract

Background: Hypertension is a significant public health problem globally, its prevalence and incidence are commonly seen in the Mideast countries, particularly in Saudi Arabia. It is a chronic disease that can harm many systems with its prevalence varying across different populations. The asymptomatic pattern of hypertension makes it a challenging disease. Screening for hypertension in asymptomatic individuals is crucial for early detection and management to prevent complications. **Aim:** we aim in our study to clarify prevalence of hypertension between asymptomatic patients during screening at primary health care centers in Saudi Arabia. **Methods:** In Riyadh, Saudi Arabia, Prince Sultan Medical City, observational research was carried out. Participants in the study were asymptomatic people getting regular checkups at primary health care centers. Blood pressure (BP) was taken using standardized protocols, with hypertension being defined as a systolic blood pressure (SBP) reading of at least 140 millimeters of mercury and/or a diastolic blood pressure (DBP) measurement of no fewer than 90 millimeters of mercury. Data were collected and analyzed to determine the prevalence of hypertension individuals in the study population. **Results:** A total of three hundred asymptomatic patients were incorporated into the study. The mean patient age was 41.22 years, with 25.7 % being male and 74.3 % female. The overall incidence of hypertension between asymptomatic patients during screening was found to be 20%. Subgroup analysis using age, sex, and other relevant factors will also be presented in the final report. **Conclusion:** Our study sheds light on the high incidence of hypertension among asymptomatic individuals during evaluation at primary health care centers in Prince Sultan Medical City, Saudi Arabia. The findings underline the importance of routine BP screening in the early identification and treatment of hypertension, which reduces the prevalence of cardiovascular disease in the general population.

More Information

How to cite this article: Alqahtani T, Hakami M, Alqahtani A, Alotaibi M, Alhussain A, Albattal S, Kofi M. Prevalence of Hypertension among Asymptomatic Patients During Screening in the Primary Health Care Center, Riyadh, Saudi Arabia. Eur J Med Health Res, 2024;2(5):52-7.

DOI: 10.59324/ejmhr.2024.2(5).05

Keywords:

Hypertension,
Asymptomatic Patients,
Screening,
Primary Health Care Centers,
Observational Study,
Cross-sectional Study,
Prevalence,
Blood Pressure,
Cardiovascular Health,
Public Health,
Risk Factors,
Health Screening.

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Introduction

Hypertension is a significant medical disease all over the world. It is high-risk factor for a diversity of health problems that need attention, including heart disease, stroke, and chronic kidney disease [1-3]. It is an ongoing, progressive illness that takes several years to develop. Hypertension can affect various organs and cause a range of disorders; therefore, identifying risk factors such as weight, smoking, physical activity, and age is vital [1].

However, many individuals are not aware that they have high BP due to the asymptomatic nature of the condition. Therefore, medical professionals ought to promote ambulatory BP monitoring. It is important to counsel patients to modify their lifestyle in order to lower their risk of consequences from hypertension [3]. Furthermore, hypertension is well-known for its huge influence on medical and human expenditures, which may be decreased with proper BP management [4].

Chronically elevated BP causes hypertensive heart disease. Hypertension, defined by the 2017 According to the American Cardiology Association and the American Heart Association, high BP is defined as a systolic pressure of 120 mm Hg or a diastolic pressure of 80 mm Hg or higher. Every 20mmHg systolic and 10mmHg diastolic pressure rise above a baseline BP of 115/75 raises the risk for cardiovascular mortality and chronic kidney illness [5,6]. Hypertension cause early mortality globally, affecting up to one in every four men and one in every five women - a total of over 1.13 billion people worldwide have hypertension. The burden of hypertension is carried disproportionately by low- and middle-income nations, which account for two-thirds of all cases [7].

Numerous papers have been done in different nations to determine the prevalence of hypertension. The prevalence of hypertension was found to be twenty eight percent in North America and forty four percent in Europe at the 140/90 mm Hg threshold in a study conducted in six European countries, Canada, and the United States [8]. A study conducted in North India revealed an alarmingly high prevalence of hypertension, particularly among adult cases that were undiagnosed or untreated. Based on a SR&MA study conducted in 2014, the overall prevalence of hypertension in Asia was found to be 27% [9].

Mansour M. Al-Nozha conducted a community-based study in Saudi Arabia in 2007 that had 17,230 participants, all of whom were in the 30- to 70-year-old age range. There were 26.1% of people with hypertension [10]. In addition, El Bcheraoui et al. assessed the prevalence of hypertension in Saudi Arabia by a national multistage survey in 2013 among a total of 10,735 participants, finding that 15% of Saudis had hypertension, 40% had borderline hypertension,

and up to 56% of hypertensive Saudis were undiagnosed [11].

The US Preventive Services Task Force (USPSTF) commissioned a systematic review to evaluate the benefits and harms of screening for hypertension in adults. The USPSTF concludes with high certainty that screening for hypertension using office-based BP measurement, home BP monitoring, or ambulatory BP monitoring in adults provides more effective control of hypertension and reduces complications [12].

The Saudi Hypertension Management Society (SHMS) recommends that all persons 18 years of age and older have their BP measured at each visit. Adults 40 years of age or older, those who are overweight or obese, and those who have high-normal BP (130–139/85–89 mm Hg) are all at elevated risk of high BP and should undergo screening every year. Every three to five years, those without additional risk factors should get rescreened [13].

Methods

Design: This study utilized an observational cross-sectional design to assess the prevalence of hypertension among asymptomatic patients during screening at primary health care centers in Prince Sultan Medical City, Saudi Arabia.

Study Setting: The study was conducted at primary health care centers within Prince Sultan Medical City, a tertiary care hospital located in Riyadh, Saudi Arabia.

Study Population: The study included asymptomatic who are undiagnosed patients aged 18–80 years who presented for routine health check-ups and were willing to participate in BP screening.

Data and Collection: A simple random sampling method will be used. By using the number generator application. Which if the number is more than 0.5 will be included, if less than 0.5 will be excluded.

Trained healthcare professionals conducted BP measurements using standardized techniques recommended by the American Heart Association. BP was measured in sitting position after a minimum 5 minutes of rest, with suitable cuff sizes for accuracy. Both systolic and diastolic blood were measured in millimeters of mercury. Data on demographics such as age, gender, and relevant medical history (where available) were also obtained.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria: Participants aged 18–80 years who were undiagnosed with hypertension were included. Participants diagnosed with Hypertension or currently on antihypertension medication were excluded.

Study setting and duration: The study was conducted at Primary health care clinics in Prince Sultan Military Medical City Covering Riyadh region, during the period from 2022 to 2023.

Sample size and Sampling Technique: No previous study done, the population proportion was 50% with a 5% margin of error and 95% confidence, the estimated number of individuals who participated in this study was 300. The formula used to calculate the sample size is the single proportion formula ($n = (Z_{\alpha/2})^2 p(1-p) / d^2$).

After calculating the formula, we got 300 patients.

Sampling Technique: the sample size was 300 males and females who attend Primary health care clinics. Patients meeting inclusion criteria were only included.

Data Analysis: Descriptive statistics were utilized to summarize the study population's demographic parameters, such as age, gender distribution, and hypertension prevalence. The prevalence of hypertension was determined as the proportion of persons who met the hypertension criterion out of the total number of participants. Subgroup analyses by age, gender, and other relevant characteristics were also used to investigate potential correlations.

Ethical Considerations: This study was done according to the principles mentioned in the Declaration of Helsinki. The IRB of Prince Sultan Medical City in Riyadh,

Saudi Arabia, provided ethical approval. All individuals provided informed consent before being included in the study.

Results

Based on Table 1, the study population consists of 300 individuals. Among them, 223 (74.3%) are female, and 77 (25.7%) are male. (See fig1)

Table 1: Gender Distribution among Study Population

	Frequency	Percent
Female	223	74.35%
Male	77	25.7%
Total	300	100.0%

Table 2 summarizes descriptive statistics for a variety of study variables, including age, systolic and diastolic blood pressure, height, weight, and BMI. The mean age was 41.22 ± 11.017 . The average systolic and diastolic blood pressure were 124.93 ± 16.644 and 75.57 ± 10.785 , respectively.

Figure 1: Gender distribution among Study Population

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics of Study Variables

	Age	Systolic	Diastolic	Height	Weight	BMI
Number	=	300				
Mean	41.22	124.93	75.57	158.9669	77.3409	30.78
Std. Error of Mean	.636	.961	.623	.5221389	1.039	.394
Median	41.00	123.00	76.00	157	75	30.00
Mode	41	121	77	157.	72	26
Std. Deviation	11.017	16.644	10.785	9.049	18.00127	6.820
Variance	121.385	277.022	116.306	81.789	324.046	46.518
Skewness	.274	.614	.251	.489	.680	.717
Std. Error of Skewness	.141	.141	.141	.141	.141	.141
Kurtosis	-.481	.288	-.245	-.290	.927	1.474
Std. Error of Kurtosis	.281	.281	.281	.281	.281	.281
Range	52	100	57	5	120	50
Minimum	20	90	52	135	36	15
Maximum	72	190	109	188	156	65

As according to fig 2, 80% of the sample have hypertension. 117 participants (39.0%) were normal, 123 participants (41.0%) were prehypertensive, 51

participants (17.0%) were stage 1, 8 participants (2.7%) were stage 2, and only 1 participant (0.3%) was stage 3 as shown in table 3.

Fig2: Frequency Distribution of Hypertension According to Systolic Blood Pressure Measurement Diagnosed on Screening

Table 3: Frequency Distribution of Hypertension Systolic Group among Study Population

	Frequency	Percent
N	117	39.0
Pre-Hypertension	123	41.0
Stage 1 Hypertension	51	17.0
Stage 2 Hypertension	8	2.7
Stage 3 Hypertension	1	.3
Total	300	100%

Cross tab between Hypertension in the Diastolic groups and Hypertension in the Systolic groups. Table 4 presents the distribution of individuals across different categories based on both systolic and diastolic blood pressure levels.

Table 4: Systolic Vs Diastolic groups Crosstabulation

			Hypertension Diastolic groups				Total
			Normal	Pre-Hypertension	Stage 1 Hypertension	Stage2 Hypertension	
Hypertension group	Normal	Count	109	8	0	0	117
		% within Systolic group	93.2%	6.8%	0.0%	0.0%	100.0%
		% within High Diastolic	57.4%	9.5%	0.0%	0.0%	39.0%
	Pre-Hypertension	Count	69	50	4	0	123
		% within Systolic group	56.1%	40.7%	3.3%	0.0%	100.0%
		% within High Diastolic	36.3%	59.5%	19.0%	0.0%	41.0%
	Stage 1 hypertension	Count	12	24	13	2	51
		% within Systolic group	23.5%	47.1%	25.5%	3.9%	100.0%
		% within Diastolic group	6.3%	28.6%	61.9%	40.0%	17.0%

	Stage 2 hypertension	Count	0	2	4	2	8
		% within Systolic group	0.0%	25.0%	50.0%	25.0%	100.0%
		% within Diastolic group	0.0%	2.4%	19.0%	40.0%	2.7%
	Stage 3 Hypertension	Count	0	0	0	1	1
		% within Systolic group	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%
		% within Diastolic group	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	20.0%	0.3%
Total	Count	190	84	21	5	300	
	% within Systolic group	63.3%	28.0%	7.0%	1.7%	100.0%	
	% within Diastolic group	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	

Discussion

The demographic composition of the sample population is notable, with a significant majority being females (74.3%). This gender disparity could be explored further to understand potential underlying factors contributing to differences in BP patterns between genders. Additionally, the mean age of 41.22 years suggests that the sample represents a relatively mature population, which may have implications for the prevalence and management of hypertension. The distribution of BP readings within the sample reveals a mean systolic blood pressure of 124.93 mmHg and a mean diastolic blood pressure of 75.57 mmHg. These values provide valuable insights into the overall BP profile of the studied population and can serve as reference points for assessing individual BP readings. The prevalence of hypertension within the sample is notable, with (41.0%) of participants classified as prehypertensive, (17.0%) classified as stage 1 hypertensive, and smaller percentages falling into more severe stages of hypertension. These findings underscore the importance of early detection and management of hypertension, particularly given its association with cardiovascular disease and other health complications.

The observed prevalence rates of hypertension have significant implications for public health and clinical practice. They highlight the need for targeted interventions aimed at promoting awareness, screening, and management of hypertension within the population [14]. Early detection and lifestyle modifications, such as dietary changes and increased physical activity, can play a crucial role in preventing the progression of hypertension and reducing the burden of related health conditions [15].

Gender disparities in BP levels and hypertension prevalence warrant further investigation. Biological

differences, hormonal factors, and social determinants of health may contribute to variations in BP patterns between males and females [16]. Understanding these disparities is essential for tailoring interventions and healthcare strategies to address the specific needs of different demographic groups.

The association between age and BP levels is well-established, with BP typically increasing with age. The mean age of the sample population aligns with this trend, emphasizing the importance of age-specific approaches to hypertension prevention and management. Healthcare providers should consider age-related risk factors and comorbidities when developing treatment plans for hypertensive individuals [17].

The findings of this study have direct clinical relevance for healthcare providers involved in the management of hypertension. They underscore the importance of routine BP monitoring, early detection of hypertension, and proactive intervention to prevent complications. Healthcare professionals should consider individual risk factors and tailor treatment approaches to optimize BP control and reduce the risk of cardiovascular events.

Limitations and Future Directions

While the study provides valuable insights into BP patterns within the sample population, several limitations should be acknowledged. These may include the relatively small sample size, potential selection bias, and the cross-sectional nature of the study design. Future research could explore longitudinal trends in blood pressure, investigate the impact of interventions on hypertension outcomes, and examine additional factors influencing BP regulation, such as genetics and environmental factors.

Public Health Implications

The public health implications of the study findings are significant, emphasizing the need for population-level

interventions to address hypertension prevalence and associated health risks. Public health initiatives focused on promoting healthy lifestyle behaviors, increasing access to preventive healthcare services, and implementing policies to reduce salt intake and encourage physical activity can help mitigate the burden of hypertension on society.

Conclusion

This study provides valuable insights into the studied population's BP patterns and hypertension prevalence. The findings underscore the importance of ongoing efforts to raise awareness, improve screening and diagnosis, and implement evidence-based interventions to manage hypertension and reduce the associated morbidity and mortality effectively.

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